

English for specific purposes curriculum evaluation from the social semiotic perspective

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an evaluation of an English for specific purposes (ESP) curriculum using the social semiotic perspective. This perspective highlights the importance of authenticity, multimodality, and communicative competence in ESP teaching and learning. Five main components of the ESP curriculum at the Port and Shipping Management Department of a Maritime Polytechnic in Indonesia were evaluated, including the syllabus, lesson plans, resources, teaching activities, and assessment. In conducting the evaluation, the authors developed an evaluation framework based on three existing frameworks, namely Stufflebeam's context input process product (CIPP) model for evaluation, Kaewpet's ESP program evaluation, and Tsou and Chen's ESP program evaluation. Multiple data collection methods were used and multiple perspectives of research participants were invited. The findings of the study revealed that there were several problems in the ESP curriculum of the Port and Shipping Management Department. The main problem was the poorly designed syllabus that has caused drawbacks on the other components, such as irrelevant and unauthentic teaching materials and activities, low variety of teaching media, lack of multimodal resources used in the classroom, and low validity and reliability of assessments. Pedagogical implications regarding the results of the evaluation are also discussed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In vocational education, the role of English for specific purposes (ESP) is highly significant. Different from English for general purposes, ESP is designed more specifically. Focusing on students' needs, ESP takes into account the complex nature of communication in a real work setting, covering language skills and competency in different contexts [1].

Due to its specificity, ESP courses will significantly differ from one field to another. An illustration was given by Basturkmen [2] who compared different courses received by an air traffic controller and an engineer because of their different communicative needs. If language is considered a tool used for communication, teaching a language is not simply teaching 'things' in the language. Careful selection and consideration must be made in designing the ESP program. The primary goal of learning should be the student's ability to communicate effectively in their future workplace [3]–[5].

The design of an ESP program is reflected in the curriculum, which shows the planning and implementation of the program. According to Mickan [6], there are five main components of a curriculum:

syllabus, work plans, resources (texts, tools, and materials), teaching activities, and assessment, in which each component contributes to the quality of the program. The curriculum is fundamental that it is considered “the heart” of a course. To achieve high-quality ESP teaching, it is important to have a good curriculum [7].

Nevertheless, many studies revealed that ESP teaching has faced various challenges. The main criticism was the curriculum of ESP which is considered too general and has caused difficulties for teachers to focus on relevant lessons needed by students [8]. In addition to that, the materials discussed in the classroom were often not attractive since they were not authentic content of the workplace texts. This has resulted in obstacles for students when they deal with real communication in the workplace [9]. To make it worse, the qualification of ESP teachers has not met expectations, where the limited content knowledge or technical knowledge of the subject becomes the main issue [10]. Teachers’ low pedagogical and professional competencies also have resulted in poor teaching instruction [11], poor assessment [12], and an uncomfortable atmosphere in the classroom [13]. It is also criticized that ESP teaching mostly involved translation of the technical terminologies from English to the mother tongue (or vice versa) with little or lack of meaningful interaction among students [14].

Realizing the potential challenges of ESP teaching, the evaluation of the ESP curriculum becomes highly important to make sure that students’ needs can be fulfilled optimally. In ESP curriculum design, evaluation is considered an inseparable process. It is one of the key components of ESP teaching [15]. Evaluation can be used to identify whether the goals of ESP courses have been accomplished and to help in giving recommendations and making decisions related to the improvement of a course [16].

A number of scholars have given significant contributions to the research regarding evaluation. Stufflebeam [17] proposed the so-called context input process product (CIPP) model of evaluation. The CIPP model consists of four complementary sets of evaluation studies: context, inputs, process, and products [18]. The four different dimensions can be applied as a whole of the evaluation process, but they can also be used separately to adjust the needs of the evaluation [19]. Context evaluation is aimed to identify and define program goals and priorities by assessing needs, problems, assets, and opportunities that are related to the program [18]. The results are used to provide initial information for the next phase of evaluation [19]. Input evaluation is aimed to assess system capabilities and find alternative strategies or services. Evaluators can identify and assess available human and material resources, conduct a literature review, or consult with experts [18], [19]. Process evaluation is used to investigate the implementation of a program. The purposes of process evaluation are to identify weaknesses in the implementation of a program, to record events and activities, and to provide information for making a decision or policy regarding the program [19]. Product evaluation is aimed to identify and assess program outcomes, their impact, and their effectiveness. It is used to identify whether the objectives set at the beginning of the program can be fulfilled [18].

Kaewpet [20] provided a more specific model of evaluation to evaluate an ESP program. He argued that in ESP courses, need analysis becomes the fundamental element in evaluation. There are several main principles in identifying learners’ needs. Firstly, learners’ communication needs must become a priority. Secondly, equal attention must be given to the learning needs. Thirdly, the “context of communication” must be taken into account. Besides that, inviting multiple perspectives in the evaluation is important, in which exploring the stakeholders’ points of view is highly necessary. In addition to that, the use of multiple data collection methods is also encouraged.

Tsou and Chen [16] proposed another framework in which the importance of learners’ needs and authenticity in ESP course evaluation is given a highlight. Prior to the evaluation, a need analysis must be conducted. Students, English teachers, curriculum developers, senior management of the faculties, sponsors, and workplaces can be considered stakeholders in which their voices are essential. Similar to [16], [20] also believe that involving multiple perspectives is prominent and there are three primary aspects that need to be addressed when conducting ESP course evaluation: the fulfillment of the learners’ needs, the authenticity of the materials used in the classroom, and the learners’ autonomy in learning.

In doing evaluation, the social semiotic perspective can provide advantages to be used as the theoretical lens. It was Halliday in 1978 who first introduced the term “social-semiotic”. He viewed social semiotics as an intellectual stance or a conceptual angle to view a problem. It concerns the relationships between language and social structure. Using social semiotics as a perspective means focusing on how people manage the use of semiotic resources in specific social practices [21], [22]. Mican [6] defined semiotic resources as “texts, materials, and tools which are used to participate in community practices”, while social practices are “people’s acts of living and working in the communities”. In the field of language learning, the social-semiotic perspective sees language learning as learning to take part in community practices with language. To engage in the communities, students need to learn to use semiotic resources which are different in each community and have to understand and interpret signs and actions which are used to communicate. In this case, it is not possible to separate context and language. Since the goal of the ESP is to prepare students to communicate effectively in their professional working lives, it is best to use the social-semiotic perspective

to evaluate the ESP course. The information about how language is used in specific contexts and communities is very important in ESP.

As we know, the development of communication and information technology has brought significant changes in the way people communicate and complete their tasks in the workplace. Technological advancements have facilitated and improved both personal and business communication. There are changes in terms of speed, cost, quality, style, and accessibility [23]. There are also impacts on social practices and interaction. Nowadays, there are various media options that can be used for communication. People can interact and exchange messages by utilizing sophisticated technology. Things that seemed impossible in the past, now become possible [24]. Technology has unlocked additional means of communication, allowing wider connections across communities, cultures, and countries [25].

To anticipate the changes, it is important to ensure that the ESP curriculum can support the students to master the knowledge and skills needed to perform their tasks as professionals. Students must be equipped with the ability to adjust and adapt to changes and innovations [26]. In vocational education, this issue becomes fundamental since the students are expected to be ready to work in the industry once they graduate. In this case, evaluation can provide valuable information for improvements.

This paper presents an evaluation of an ESP curriculum in the port and shipping management department using the social-semiotic perspective. The evaluation was aimed to see whether the curriculum is effective in addressing the student's needs. In conducting evaluations, most scholars agreed on the significance of need analysis. However, studies that discussed social-semiotic as a perspective in evaluation are not available yet. This study attempts to fill the gap by using the social-semiotic perspective to evaluate an ESP curriculum. According to this perspective, it is important to understand social practices and semiotic resources used in the target community when performing need analysis and evaluation. Five primary components of the ESP curriculum were evaluated, including syllabus, lesson plans, teaching resources (teaching materials and media), teaching activities, and assessment. The pedagogical implications are also discussed.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design and evaluation framework

In conducting the research, the authors used the case study evaluation based on Yin [27]. There are several considerations for choosing the method. Firstly, it enables the authors to gather information from multiple sources of evidence, including observation, interviews, focus group discussions, documents, and archives. Secondly, it offers a richness of data because the authors attempted to collect data at the site of the study to explore and understand the phenomena in its real-life context, without making any interventions.

An evaluation framework was used as a guide for evaluation. The research adapted three evaluation frameworks: Stufflebeam's CIPP model for evaluation [17], Kaewpet's ESP program evaluation [20], and Tsou and Chen's ESP program evaluation [16]. The CIPP model was used as the main framework. In the context evaluation, the authors investigated "the context" or the workplaces related to Port and Shipping Management Department. As the social-semiotic perspective was chosen, the social practices and the use of English in the port and shipping management community were explored. In the input evaluation, the authors reviewed the syllabus and the lesson plans. In the process evaluation, the authors investigated the implementation of the teaching activities in the classroom, teaching resources (consisting of teaching materials and media), and assessment. In the product evaluation, the authors reviewed the relation of all components affecting students' language learning. Kaewpet's framework was used to provide consideration on who should be involved in the evaluation and what methods are used in each phase of evaluation. While based on Tsou and Chen's framework, the authors considered three aspects when evaluating the ESP program: stakeholders' goals or needs, learners' needs, and authenticity. The evaluation framework used in this study can be seen in Figure 1.

2.2. Research context

Port and Shipping Management Department is a study program in a Maritime Polytechnic in Indonesia. The students are prepared to work in the port and shipping business, as well as in the field of logistics and export-import business. English is taught every semester in this study program, except in semesters 5 and 6 when students have their internship program in the port and shipping industries. English course in each semester has a different syllabus.

2.3. Research participants

The evaluation model involved multiple perspectives of participants. In the first phase, the head of the study program, alumni of the port and shipping management department, and a number of stakeholders were invited to participate as research participants. In the second, third, and fourth phases, the authors involved the head of the professional certification agency, three English teachers, and five students of the

port and shipping management department. The selection of the research participants was based on a purposive sampling technique. The authors purposefully selected the participants who were considered to be able to provide information and help the authors understand the phenomena [28].

Figure 1. The evaluation framework adapted from Stufflebeam's CIPP model for evaluation, Kaewpet's ESP program evaluation, and Tsou and Chen's ESP program evaluation

2.4. Data collection and analysis

In collecting data, the authors used multiple methods of data collection. In the first phase, the social practices and the use of English in the port and shipping management community were explored. The authors distributed a questionnaire to the alumni and conducted an interview with several participants, including alumni, stakeholders, and the head of the study program. The findings of the first phase indicated that authenticity, multimodality, and communicative competence are fundamental aspects of ESP evaluation, and therefore were taken into account in making the instruments for evaluation in the next phases. The report of the first phase of the research has been published in a separate research article by Sari *et al.* [29].

At the end of phase 1, the authors designed an evaluation checklist to evaluate five different components of the ESP curriculum based on the theories of some scholars. There were some of the scholars whose views and theories were used as references in the instrument development [6], [30]–[35]. To ensure the validity and reliability of the instruments, the authors conducted two steps when designing the instruments. Firstly, we prepared a blueprint outlining the elements of evaluation, descriptions of each element and indicators. Secondly, we conducted a pilot test. The content validity of the research instrument was examined by involving two experts: an associate professor in the language education field who is an expert in curriculum development and the head of the professional certification body for port and shipping management. Before being used for the research, the blueprint and the instruments were checked. We made some revisions after obtaining corrections from the experts.

The reliability of the checklists was tested using test-retest reliability, in which the authors conducted the measurement twice with an interval of two months. As suggested Mohajan [36], the interval of the two measurements should not be very long to avoid changes during the second test which affects the reliability. The result of the Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.80 which indicates that the checklist has a high reliability.

In the second phase, the authors collected the syllabi and lesson plans of the ESP course of the port and shipping management department. At this stage, the head of the professional certification body was involved in an interview to review the topics in the syllabi. Five senior students were also involved in a focus group discussion to give their perspectives. Both the interview and the focus group discussion were recorded and transcribed.

In the third phase, classroom observations were conducted. The authors observed the teaching activities, the teaching resources (teaching media and teaching materials), and the assessment. The activities in the classroom were recorded after obtaining permission from the teachers. The authors also collected and examined the teaching materials and assessments. In the fourth phase, the authors explored the relationship among the components affecting ESP teaching. We used the information obtained from the previous phases to analyze the relationship and used a fishbone diagram to illustrate the findings.

Methodological triangulation was used to minimize bias or confounding variables that might threaten the validity. In conducting the evaluation, the authors employed observation, interview, and document review to confirm the findings. If the three methods show the same conclusions, then validity is established [37]. At the end of the last evaluation phase, the authors conducted member check by involving three English teachers in a focus group discussion to discuss the findings. This step is important to ensure the accuracy of the findings and improve validity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings and discussion are presented in several parts. At the beginning, the researchers explain the evaluation of each component. After that, we discuss how the components together affect ESP teaching.

3.1. The syllabus evaluation

In the syllabus evaluation, there were several aspects examined: the description of the course rationale, the description of the entry and exit level, the description of aims and objectives, the selection of the course content, the arrangement of the scope and sequence, and the course structures. The study revealed that the syllabus of the English for the Port and Shipping Management Department needs a lot of improvement. Many fundamental aspects were missing and not properly formulated. Firstly, the course rationale was not described clearly. In the majority of the parts, the descriptions were too general and insufficient. According to Richards [31], the course description should be specific and unique. It should also describe the beliefs, values, and goals that underlie the course. From the social semiotic perspective, the course rationale should be related to the social practices that students will perform in their future workplaces.

Secondly, the description of the entry and exit levels of students was not available. In addition to that, the aims and objectives of the course were not described specifically. They also did not reflect communication in the port and shipping community. Therefore, they could not provide direction and information about what should be achieved in the course. Thus, it caused difficulties for the lecturers to plan and arrange their lessons. A good syllabus functions like a reliable map, which provides an effective direction to the teachers when teaching. This finding supports previous studies [38], [39] who found that the unavailability of proper plans can impact the quality of teaching practices. On the other hand, a good and systematic teaching and learning procedure will allow students to experience learning in the most effective way.

Another problem was the selection of the course content, which is perceived as the most prominent aspect of ESP teaching. In ESP, students' communication needs should become the main consideration when deciding on materials to teach. The evaluation revealed that some topics in the syllabi needed to be revised because they were too general and did not reflect the communication in the Port and Shipping community. In this case, inviting stakeholders' perspectives when designing the syllabus will be very. This study agrees with the findings of some scholars that involving stakeholders in syllabus design can help to improve the effectiveness of ESP teaching [40]–[45]. There are a lot of materials to learn in the English language and it is essential to select and focus on the most important items which appear frequently in communication in the specific community.

The arrangement of the scope and sequence and the course structures also need considerable improvements. The social semiotic perspective recommends the use of social practices as the basis to organize the syllabus. Using social practices as the framework offers great advantages for ESP teaching [6]. Firstly, it is easier to clarify the purpose of an activity. By using social practices as the basis, the teaching and learning activities will be more meaningful for students since the learning objectives are clear and specific. When practicing reporting a problem in delivery to the customer, students can learn various aspects; for example, the grammar of past tense and connecting words to express cause-and-effect relationships. Students can also learn formulaic expressions in telling problems to other people. The activity of learning grammar and practicing formulaic expressions will be more meaningful for students because they know the purpose of learning the materials. This also highlights the importance of learning grammar in context.

Secondly, using social practices as the syllabus framework enables the lecturers to bring authenticity closer into the classroom. This can combat the criticism that many classroom activities do not represent "the real world." Applying the social semiotic perspective in the syllabus design means that the selection of topics and activities is based on a community and its practices. The teachers can exploit documents used in the

community such as forms, letters, emails, and catalogs, in the classroom as teaching materials. Therefore, the teaching and learning activity will be more authentic and motivating for the students.

3.2. The lesson plan evaluation

Lesson plans describe teachers' intended instructional actions in a course of study so that there is cohesion and direction in instruction. There were several aspects evaluated in the lesson plan, including the goal and objectives, materials and equipment, procedures of teaching, and evaluation. The authors tried to collect the lesson plan for all semesters but only found one lesson plan which is made for semester 7 class. The teachers admitted that their teaching load and additional workload have caused them difficulties in making a proper lesson plan according to the format set by the institution. They arranged plans for their teaching activity, but the plans were not written systematically.

One of the most important components of the lesson plan is the learning goals or objectives. The learning goals state the overall purpose that teachers will attempt to accomplish by the end of the class period. They should reflect the social practices of the port and shipping community as the target group in which students will participate in the future [6]. The objectives, which are derived from the learning goals should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound. The lesson plan analyzed in this study was made for twelve meetings. Each meeting has different activities and topics to be discussed. However, the goals and the objectives of the lesson plans do not reflect the social practices in the port and shipping community. The learning objectives are not specific and difficult to be measured.

The second main component in the lesson plan is the materials and equipment. Good planning requires the teachers to think carefully about what they need to bring with them to the classroom, including the materials and the equipment needed to deliver the lesson. From the social semiotic perspective, the materials and equipment should support the students' need to communicate in a multimodal way. However, in the lesson plan, the teaching equipment is not described clearly. The materials are mostly reading texts which do not support the students' needs to be involved in multimodal communication.

The next component is the procedures of teaching. There are five phases of a lesson plan that need to be followed to achieve effective teaching [46]. The first is the opening where the teacher gives a preview of the new lesson by addressing the students' previous activity or knowledge. The second is stimulation where the teacher helps students to relate the new lesson to their previous knowledge. The third is instruction or participation where the teacher presents the activities in the classroom. The fourth is closure where the teacher checks what the students have learned. The last is follow-up where the teacher reinforces some concepts and sometimes introduces some new ones. However, in the lesson plan, the procedure of teaching is not described well. There is only a little information about the teaching strategies without any clear description of how the teaching will be conducted.

The last component is evaluation. Evaluation is important to determine whether the learning objectives have been accomplished. In the lesson plan, it is important to mention how the evaluation will be conducted. An evaluation plan will provide good guidance for lecturers during the teaching and learning process. However, information about how the evaluation will be conducted is not clearly written in the lesson plans.

In education, the lesson plan should reflect the activities that happen in the classroom. Based on the evaluation, the lesson plans did not represent all of the classroom activities since the activities were not described clearly. The absence of good lesson plans can bring negative consequences to the teaching and learning process. Many scholars agree that a good plan will function like an accurate map, which provides an effective direction to the teachers when teaching. Good lesson plans will enable the teachers to design logical and systematic teaching and learning procedures to enable students to experience learning in the most effective way.

3.3. The teaching resources evaluation

The teaching resources comprised the teaching materials and teaching media. The review showed that mostly the teaching materials were relevant to the field of port and shipping management. However, the materials given in semester 1 needed considerable revisions. Some of the materials were too general and therefore did not reflect the characteristic of English for specific purposes which should be related to the student's specific needs. This study agrees with a number of scholars who suggest that the teaching materials in ESP classrooms should be rich with technical vocabulary to support students' communication practices in their future workplace [47]–[50].

However, it is interesting to note that in some classes, the teachers did not use the syllabus when selecting or designing the teaching materials. As mentioned previously, the deficiencies in the syllabus have caused difficulties for the teachers in planning their lessons. Therefore, they improvised by using their background knowledge and experience to select relevant teaching materials for students.

The teachers also had shown an attempt to use authentic materials in their classrooms, even though they were not consistent in addressing authenticity. The teachers admitted that they had difficulties in finding authentic materials due to insufficient experience working in the port and shipping industry. Mostly, they graduated from English department and immediately worked as English teachers. This caused them having lack technical or content knowledge in the port and shipping management field. A study related to this issue has been conducted [10] and the current study strengthens their findings that inadequate content knowledge or technical knowledge has hindered teachers in providing authentic materials in their classrooms.

Regarding the use of teaching media, the findings revealed that most teachers utilized various media during the teaching and learning process. They tried to provide students with materials from multimodal sources. Various diagrams, photos, audio, and videos were used in the classrooms. This was shown especially in semesters 2, 3, 4, and 8 in which the teachers used multimedia devices such as laptops, LCD projectors, and multimedia speakers in their classrooms. They also used various online learning platforms and a combination of text, images, audio, and videos as the media for teaching. However, in semesters 1 and 7, the lecturers did not explore various media. The exploitations of images or pictures, audio, and video in the classroom to facilitate students' learning were minimal.

In language teaching, the use of teaching media should consider the advancement of technology since it affects the way people communicate. As we know that the internet has brought significant changes in communication [51]. Nowadays, people generally use various media to convey their messages. It is very common to find written verbal texts intertwined with visual/images or audio. The massive use of digital devices has made multimodal texts more popular. As a consequence, providing multimodal resources, using various teaching media, and utilizing digital technology in classroom practices are highly important. It is necessary to give students the opportunity to explore various media resources to learn and communicate their knowledge [32]. Learning from various media can raise students' awareness that there are options of media that can be used for making meaning and getting things done. In addition to that, it can provide students with richer and more varied experiences of texts. The lesson will be more meaningful for them since it reflects real communication in the community. This study supports the findings of some scholars that addressing multimodality is essential in ESP teaching. Students can learn to exploit semiotic resources other than verbal language (for example visual, audio, or audio-visual) to support them in making meaning or producing texts more effectively [34], [51]–[54].

3.4. The teaching activities evaluation

There were several aspects evaluated regarding the teaching activities: authenticity, multimodality, the teaching and learning of grammar, and communicative competence. The findings of the study indicate that some parts of the teaching and learning activities need serious improvements. The first issue dealt with the authenticity of the teaching and learning activities [6]. Students' activities should be related to the real-world uses of English in the port and shipping community. Generally, the teachers provided students with authentic activities. However, they were not consistent. Activities such as completing sentences without meaningful context should be replaced with more authentic ones.

Inauthentic activities in the classroom have a great impact on students. It can cause difficulties for them when dealing with real communication in the workplace [9]. On the other hand, classroom activities that reflect real working situations are proven to enhance students' learning motivation since they can relate the classroom activities to their communication needs [10], [55], [56]. The advantages of authenticity were also mentioned in previous studies [14], [57] who found that authenticity in classroom activities enables students to have better engagement and motivation in the lesson. It can also support the transfer of skills and knowledge from the classroom into real work practices.

Besides authenticity, multimodality becomes another fundamental aspect. In a real working situation, people nowadays often use multimodal resources in communication. People use a combination of written text, pictures, moving images, and sound which are mediated through digital devices [51]. Based on the observation of the teaching practices, multimodality was not addressed in semesters 1 and 2 classes. The teacher mostly used written verbal text in the teaching and learning process with minimal exploitation of multimodal resources during interaction in the classroom. This caused the teaching and learning activities to become less meaningful and less motivating for students and thus prevented them to receive the best learning experience.

Another aspect that needs to be considered is the teaching and learning of grammar. According to the social-semiotic perspective, grammar should not be taught separately but embedded in the text. The study of grammar should be based on the text as part of practice [6]. This can make grammar learning becomes easier and more meaningful for students because of the clear and specific context provided. This study shows that most teachers used relevant texts and provided meaningful contexts when teaching grammar. However, the activity of learning grammar at the level of sentences as found in semester 1 should be avoided.

Communicative competence is the next fundamental issue that needs improvement. This study also revealed that teachers mostly focused on linguistic competence and neglected other competence. If the final goal of language learning is to make students able to communicate effectively in the target language, the lecturers should put equal attention to all communicative competence. Students need to master various formulaic expressions to develop their linguistic resources and enhance fluency [58], [59]. Students also need to have socio-cultural and interactional competence to be able to communicate with clients who have different backgrounds and nationalities. Therefore, learning grammar or language structure is not sufficient. Knowledge about various discourses and socio-cultural aspects of the language, knowledge about various formulaic expressions, and communication strategies, are also important to support students' language learning [33].

3.5. The assessment evaluation

In the assessment evaluation, two main aspects were reviewed: validity and reliability. Based on the social semiotic perspective, the validity of the assessment is indicated by "the relationship of task and discourse specification to the social practices for which a candidate is taking the test" [6]. In other words, a test is considered valid if the tasks are relevant to the social practices in the target community and include important aspects of communication. Thus, to know whether the assessment is valid, the authors examined several aspects such as the relevance, the authenticity, and the focus of the assessment.

The findings showed that the teachers have tried to provide relevant and authentic assessments. However, they need to be more consistent and make improvements in some classes. Mostly, the teachers only assessed linguistic competence, such as accuracy of grammar and pronunciation, and neglected other aspects.

The assessments also did not include communicative competence comprehensively. From the social-semiotic perspective, communicative competence is very important for ESP students. The goal of language learning from the social-semiotic perspective is that learners can participate effectively in the social practices in the relevant community. To be able to do that, linguistic competence alone will not be enough for learners. Other competencies are needed to support the success of communication.

Another main aspect is reliability. A test will be more reliable if the questions and instructions are clear and unambiguous, and there is a consistent marking which can be achieved by providing an answer key or a well-thought scoring procedure or rubric [35]. The evaluation showed that the teachers had provided students with clear questions and instructions, however, there was no proper rubric available for the assessment. There was only one rubric used in the mid-term examination of semester 3. In an assessment, the role of a rubric is prominent since it helps to ensure that the marking is consistent, and thus enhances its reliability. The absence of a proper rubric for assessment can have a great impact on reliability.

3.6. The relationship of all components of the curriculum in affecting ESP teaching

The results of the evaluation indicate that many components of the curriculum need to be improved. The relationship among the five components is summarized using a fishbone diagram as illustrated in Figure 2. The figure shows that the absence of an appropriate syllabus has brought significant consequences. Like a domino effect, the problems in the syllabus have caused problems for other components. The teachers experienced difficulties in planning the lessons, selecting teaching materials, arranging activities for the students, and designing assessments. It is important to highlight that coherence and conformity among all components should be maintained. The learning goals stated in the syllabus should be addressed in all components and can be achieved at the end of the course.

3.7. The pedagogical implication

The findings of the study bring several pedagogical implications in ESP teaching at the port and shipping management department. The authors would like to discuss the pedagogical implications in three aspects. The first aspect deals with authenticity. There is an urgent need to redesign the syllabus by using social practices as the framework in which the involvement of stakeholders and alumni is highly significant to achieve relevance and authenticity. The social practices-based syllabus will enable the teachers to provide students with relevant and authentic materials and activities in the classroom. The teachers can improve their content knowledge by reading various books, having a discussion with discipline-related teachers, joining relevant seminars, or watching videos shared on video-sharing platforms. There are many websites and YouTube channels that provide information related to the port and shipping industry. The lecturers are encouraged to explore various resources and media to select the most suitable materials and to arrange the most appropriate activities in their classrooms.

The second aspect is multimodality. The teachers need to be aware that the advancement of technology has changed the way people communicate. Since communication nowadays is multimodal, it is suggested that teachers use various multimodal resources in the classroom. This can be done by utilizing

information technology and digital devices. However, to be able to provide multimodal activities and materials, the lecturers are required to have a special competence called multimodal design knowledge. As quoted from previous study [60], there are three interconnected aspects of teaching expertise: multimodal design knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and linguistic knowledge which all together can provide support for the lecturers in implementing their teaching practices. The current evaluation revealed that the lecturers already have adequate linguistic knowledge, but they still need to improve their multimodal design knowledge and pedagogical knowledge. Multimodal design knowledge refers to the lecturers' knowledge of utilizing multimodal resources. It may include using various features on the PowerPoint presentation to enhance the slides, using multiple colors and selecting various images to present the teaching materials, combining text and images, and utilizing audio and video to support written information.

Nevertheless, combining the materials and presenting them in a coherent and visually appealing way requires more than just combining multimodal resources. It also requires the lecturers' pedagogical knowledge to understand the pedagogical potentials offered by various media [60]. The immense use of digital devices has brought significant changes in society and thus has forced English teachers to improve their conventional teaching practices. The importance of information technology in the classrooms to support the teaching and learning process is undeniable. The finding of the study is in line with previous study [61] who are also concerned with multimodality and authenticity in ESP assessment. While another study [62] found that English teachers need to improve their digital and technological competency to maintain their professionalism.

The next fundamental aspect is communicative competence. As mentioned previously, if the goal of language learning is the student's ability to engage in communication effectively, the lecturers should address all communicative competence in the classroom. This is a kind reminder that learning a foreign language is not only learning the structure, vocabulary, or pronunciation. Linguistic competence alone is not sufficient, and students need other competence as well to support them in improving their communication skills.

Figure 2. The relationship of all components

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of the study indicate that considerable improvements in many components of the curriculum are needed. The syllabi were not properly designed and thus could not provide a guide for the teachers. Some materials were not authentic and did not represent social practices in the port and shipping management. There was also an issue related to multimodality and media used for teaching. Some classes were lack of the use of multimodal resources and had a low variety of teaching media. The issue of authenticity was also found in the teaching and learning activities. Many classroom activities did not reflect the real-world uses of English in the port and shipping management community and did not cover communicative competence comprehensively as one of the important aspects of ESP teaching. Lastly, the validity and reliability of the assessment need to be improved by designing relevant and authentic tasks, covering communicative competence in the assessment, and providing a good scoring rubric.

The evaluation reveals that the quality of the syllabus affected other components. Many problems in the classrooms happened due to the syllabus that was poorly designed. Besides the syllabus issue, the competence of the teachers also needs to be improved, especially their content knowledge, multimodal design knowledge, and pedagogical knowledge.

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